

Amino Derivatives of Tungsten(VI) Oxytetrachloride. Part II

Sarju Prasad and K. S. R. Krishnaiah

The amino derivatives of tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride have been prepared by the action of tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines, and heterocyclic bases; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

No attempt appears to have been made to study the reactions of WOCl_4 with secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases in organic solvents. Von Beck (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1931, **196**, 85) prepared some complex bromotungstites like pyridinium tetrabromotungstite $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})\text{WObR}_4$, tetraethylammonium tetrabromoquo tungstite $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}[\text{WObR}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, etc. In an earlier communication the preparation and properties of the compounds of WOCl_4 with some aromatic primary mono- and diamines have been reported (this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 352) and the work is now extended to study the action of WOCl_4 on some secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride was prepared as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The organic solvents were dehydrated and distilled. The amines and other chemicals used were of B. D. H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality.

The compounds were prepared by adding slowly a solution of the amine in benzene to WOCl_4 in CS_2 with constant shaking till the amine was in slight excess. In the case of secondary amines, the compounds formed settled down immediately, but with tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases, the compounds separated after shaking the mixture for a long time. The precipitate was filtered and washed with benzene till free of the amine. All the operations were carried out in a dry atmosphere and the products were finally dried over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator.

Tungsten, chlorine, and nitrogen were estimated as in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Compounds of tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride with heterocyclic bases.

Heterocyclic base.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Pyridine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N})_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Brown	27.53	27.96	21.37	21.55
2. Piperidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N})_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Reddish brown	27.06	26.99	20.64	20.80
3. α -Picoline	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Brown	25.64	25.77	19.42	19.86
4. γ -Picoline	Do	Light brown	25.73	25.77	19.78	19.86
5. Quinoline	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Chocolate brown	21.30	21.44	16.18	16.53
6. Piperazine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Light pink	35.53	35.80	27.56	27.60
7. 2-Aminopyridine	$[\text{WO}(\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Yellowish brown	34.19	34.71	26.40	26.76

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TUNGSTEN(VI) OXYTETRACHLORIDE

761

TABLE II

Compounds of tungsten (VI) Oxytetrachloride with secondary and tertiary amines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Methylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2)_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Light brown	24.07	23.90	19.21	18.42	..	..
2. Ethylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Ash	22.23	22.27	17.04	17.17	..	..
3. Benzylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Brown	17.40	17.13	12.97	13.20	..	..
4. Diphenylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Black	18.12	13.07	13.69	13.93	5.39	5.50
5. Diphenylbenzidine	$[\text{WO}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\}_2\text{Cl}_4]$	Light dirty green	18.40	18.14	13.47	13.66	..	..
6. Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -phenylene diamine	$[\text{WO}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\}_2\text{Cl}_4]$	Violet	29.82	29.98	22.72	23.10	9.05	9.12
7. Dimethylaniline	$[\text{WO}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Ash	22.13	22.27	17.43	17.17	6.54	6.78
8. Diethylamine	$[\text{WO}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\}_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Grey	19.07	19.62	15.07	15.12	..	..
9. Dibenzylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2)_4\text{Cl}_4]$	Brown	20.48	20.72	15.83	15.97	8.09	8.16
10. <i>p</i> -Aminodimethylaniline	$[\text{WO}(\text{Me}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2)_2\text{Cl}_4]$	Dark brown	26.71	26.96	23.20	23.10	9.04	9.12
11. <i>p</i> -Aminodimethylaniline	$[\text{WO}(\text{Et}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2)_2\text{Cl}_4]$	Black	26.03	27.48	20.72	21.16	..	..

DISCUSSION

The compounds formed with tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride and aromatic secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases are similar to those formed with aromatic primary amines. These are insoluble in benzene and ether but sparingly soluble in CS_2 , ethanol, and acetone. The compounds are considerably stable in dry atmosphere, but when exposed to moist air they absorb moisture and decompose. Those obtained with tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases are very hygroscopic. These are decomposed by acids and alkalis.

On heating alone, the compounds afford a sublimate which is soluble in water, is acidic, and responds to the test for Cl and the corresponding organic base. When heated with sodalime, the corresponding amine or heterocyclic base separates out.

The compounds formed with dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine, diphenylbenzidine, *p*-aminodimethylaniline, *p*-aminodiethylaniline, 2-aminopyridine, and piperazine are considerably stable, due to the formation of chelate compounds.

The structures of these compounds appear to be similar to those formed with primary amines as shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

It is interesting to note that only two molecules of dibenzylaniline combine with one molecule of WOCl_4 , which is probably due to steric hindrance.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing the necessary facilities.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

Received February 27, 1961.